

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Salem Hussein****FIRST NAME: Ahmed Yahya****PROGRAM CODE: DIFE****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **In academic writing, what are the steps after you do some research, note making and draw up a second plan?**

- Decide on a possible answer to the question (in terms of the research you have done).
- Look through your notes and choose examples to provide evidence to support your answer.
- Write all this down in point form and this will be your essay plan.
- All answers are correct.¹**

2. **In academic writing, how can you well-organized and fairly complete draft?**

- A reader can follow the sequence of ideas from sentence to sentence, and from paragraph to paragraph.²**

¹ EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington DC: Euclid University. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/> (accessed August 12, 2019), 3.

- Make sure the words you use do not mean what you think.
 - Check punctuation and spelling. You do not need to use dictionary.
 - Make sure that one paragraph has a clear main point that relates to the argument.
3. **After you figure out what the assignment is asking for, what are the procedures to pick your topic?**
- You can start after you head to the library by limiting your topic to reflect a special interest in it.
 - Suggest choosing a couple of topics that seem interesting to you and then doing some superficial research.³**
 - You mustn't carve out of your topic a manageable piece.
 - Pick a topic whose name sounds like an encyclopedia entry bridges, birds and masks.
4. **What are the alternatives if the researchers use data reported in secondary sources only and they can't find them in primary sources?**
- If they are doing very advanced work, they do not need to check the accuracy of facts, or numbers from secondary sources.
 - Those who publish in respected places always misreport deliberately, but they make careless mistakes more often than non-experts think.
 - They are cautious about using those secondary sources, because secondhand reports of data have a high error rate.⁴**

² Ibid, 42-46.

³ Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*, 18-23.

⁴ Ibid, 25-29

- If they were studying how the Alamo story has been analyzed, then primary sources offering those analyses would be their secondary sources.
5. **What are the steps to read through the studies and articles and the papers on your list, plan for this to take a little while you need to read and take notes as you read?**
- Take the time to read your most promising sources at least one time.
- If you were amiably but pointedly questioning a friend; imagine his or her answers, then question them.⁵**
- If you agree, don't just reject a source: read it in ways that will encourage your own original thinking.
- You probably will be able to engage your sources fully until after you have done some reading and developed a few ideas of your own.
6. **How can make a quoted sentence mesh with yours?**
- You can change its meaning.
- You clearly indicate added or changed words with circle brackets.
- Deletions with three dots (called ellipses).⁶**
- You cannot modify the quotation.
7. **Whenever we are writing the research paper in Turabian, we are going to references those resources in a different way?**

⁵ Ibid, 30-34.

⁶ Ibid, 49.

We only use parenthetical citations when a professor requires them.⁷

The typical way to format a source and Turabian is by using endnotes.

We must cite one source in a note.

We may decide to use footnotes and endnotes for substantive material that we want to include in the body of your text.

8. What are differences between qualitative research approach, and quantitative research approach?

Qualitative research approach focuses on the quality of experience trying to describe or understand the essence or nature of human experience.⁸

Qualitative research focuses on more measurable factors asking questions such as how much, how many, and how frequently.

Quantitative research is suited to promoting a deep understanding of a social setting or activity as viewed from the perspective of the research participants.

Qualitative research applied to describe current conditions, investigate relationships, and study cause-effect phenomena.

9. What are the goals of qualitative research?

⁷ Ibid, 50.

⁸ Bloomberg, Linda D. & Volpe, Marie. 2008. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 33-34

- Understand, describe, discover meaning or generate hypotheses and theory.**⁹
- Predict, control, confirm, and test hypotheses.
- The process of analysis is inductive approach.
- The initial categories of your conceptual framework were inductively obtained from the literature.

10. **What are the most common punctuation marks in English?**

- A full stop is also called a period in American English. Use a full stop at the beginning of a full sentence.
- Commas have two main jobs.
- Hyphens are used to make compound words.**¹⁰
- Semicolons are most similar to commas.

⁹ Ibid, 97.

¹⁰ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation. 2011. *A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Seventh edition. European Commission, 18-22.

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